

SPEYES: Sensing and Patrolling Enablers Yielding Effective SASO¹²³

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Abstract—This paper describes a DARPA seedling initiative that analyzed, simulated, and assessed the force-multiplying payoff potential of various ground-based C3I technologies for Stability and Support Operations (SASO). The initiative was called Sensing and Patrolling Enablers Yielding Effective SASO (SPEYES). A variety of daily-occurring threats, challenges, and manpower-intensive tasks facing ground forces performing SASO missions in a post-combat environment were identified. Moreover, a collection of existing and emerging technologies to address these threats, challenges, and tasks were characterized and modeled within a simulation framework. Using “cordon and search” as our SASO problem focus, our analysis shows that promising force-multiplying payoffs are possible using an array of low-cost sensing, situational awareness, C2 and shaping technologies. We describe these results using various performance metrics.

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1. INTRODUCTION

As recent events in Iraq have demonstrated, it is critically important to establish stability and security rapidly in a post-conflict environment to allow the nation-building activities to commence, including reconstruction, elections, winning the hearts and minds of the locals, etc. Post-conflict threats and challenges can include looting, day-to-day uncertainty for the locals, corruption, thuggery, black marketeering, etc., all of which present a significant obstacle to our forces who are responsible for Stability and Support Operations (SASO). Moreover, many physical and social aspects of the post-conflict environment increase the complexity of the planning and execution of SASO missions. These issues include the need to locate and secure weapons caches or wanted individuals, conducting negotiations with local tribal and religious leaders, responding to grievances from the locals, and dealing appropriately with insurgents.

The scope and complexity of military SASO missions can be seen from the current operations conducted by US forces in Iraq and Afghanistan. SASO missions can cover a wide range of operations for coalition forces, from large-scale openly hostile environments such as those currently found in Baghdad and Fallujah, to smaller scale more discrete operations exemplified by protection of key infrastructure and leadership facilities in and around Kabul, Afghanistan and the “Green Zone” in Baghdad, Iraq. Three SASO missions are of particular interest, namely: (i) fixed site security (check points, guard towers), (ii) mounted and

dismounted patrols, and (iii) cordon and search. These are of interest – and they are the focus of the SPEYES seedling initiative – because they are daily-occurring, manpower-intensive, and they offer an opportunity for realizing force multiplier payoffs.

SASO missions also require diverse military skill sets and roles, including peacekeeping and peace enforcing, both small and heavy arms combat, and civil affairs. There are numerous technical challenges to overcome as well. These include an enemy that is more familiar with the physical and social urban terrain than the US forces, resulting in poor situational awareness for US forces. Furthermore, tactical actions can have strategic implications where bad responses can quickly turn neutrals into enemies. US forces may experience difficulties identifying the enemy, since combatants very often intermingle with the non-combatant population. The lethality of asymmetric threats including IEDs, RPGs, VBIEDs, snipers, and suicide bombers is significantly increased. Finally, SASO missions often require highly decentralized small unit operations at the Battalion-Squad level, which poses numerous challenges to ground forces.

Figure 1. RAND study asserts 20 troops per thousand in the population are required for successful nation building.

Historically, rapid post-conflict stability has been attained through high troop densities. As Figure 1 shows, a RAND study of recent nation-building campaigns asserts that in order to be successful these efforts required approximately 20 troops per thousand in the population. For Iraq, the level of manning identified by the RAND report equates to approximately 500,000 troops, or more than three times our current level of manning⁴. A key motivating theme that led to the SPEYES effort was addressing the challenge of trying to enhance the SASO effectiveness of a limited number of forces in a highly complex, dynamic, and unpredictable post-conflict environment through various force-multiplying technologies.

⁴ This does not include coalition forces or Iraqi security forces. If both of these were considered, then approximately 400,000 troops would be in the environment.

Figure 2. Green Zone

To narrow the focus, the SPEYES seedling initiative analyzed, simulated and assessed the force-multiplying payoff potential of various ground-based C3I technologies for daily-occurring manpower-intensive SASO problems within the Green Zone (see Figure 1). The analysis and simulation was focused on the cordon and search SASO mission specifically. Key tasks that ground forces needed to perform with respect to cordon and search were identified and simulated. Several existing and emerging technologies were characterized and modeled in the simulation. The results attained were promising and they showed that force-multiplying payoffs are possible using an array of integrated sensing, situation awareness, C2 and shaping technologies. These results will be discussed, and they include numerous technical and operational performance metrics.

2. SPEYES System Overview

The process of developing the architecture for a system that addressed the SPEYES challenge was to first characterize the challenges facing troops performing the three SASO missions of fixed site security (check points, guard towers), mounted and dismounted patrols, and cordon and search. This understanding was key to investigating the force multiplier payoff potential of a collection of integrated low-cost ground-based existing and emerging C3I technologies. The following three component technologies proved to be critical in the general SPEYES system architecture:

- (i) *Sensing technologies* – low-cost, easily-emplaced, camouflaged sensors (video, acoustic, IR, EOD) to provide urban situation awareness;
- (ii) *SA/C2 technologies* – multi-echelon software tools tailored for distributed operations (planning, dynamic resource management, simulation, mission rehearsal);
- (iii) *Shaping technologies* – non-lethal, audio hot-spotting and EOD shaping tools for example to diffuse adversaries, crowds, IEDs, VBIEDs, etc.

The three SPEYES technology enablers increase the effectiveness of the forces for SASO by means of better threat detection/prediction, increased situational awareness and intelligence of the post-conflict environment (physical and social), and improved decentralized operations. For example, SPEYES technology and sensors will increase the speed and ability of U.S. forces to gather intelligence by the combined use and smart placement of visual, acoustic, spectral, and IR sensors. The information gathered from the sensor observations allows troops and commanders to gain better situational awareness and facilitates more efficient scheduling and patrolling, including the utilization of innovative shaping technologies. Better and faster observations, combined with more accurate and timely orientation, permitted better and more focused decisions leading to quicker and more effective actions on the part of the U.S. forces.

As Figure 3 illustrates, the SPEYES system architecture is

Figure 3. SPEYES Architecture

envisioned to be a ground-based, decentralized, multi-echelon C3I system comprised of Sensing, SA/C2, and Shaping technologies, and tailored for Battalion through the Squad level small unit forces. While innovative technologies and new operational concepts can present a force multiplier individually, the goal of the seedling initiative was to explore and determine the impact and force multiplier payoffs that an integrated system of varied technologies might provide. Our objective for the SPEYES system was also to distribute and aggregate information at different echelons of the military force, not simply fuse together information from different sources to provide a common operational map.

Figure 4. The Notional Effect of Force Multipliers

In terms of force multipliers, Figure 4 illustrates notionally how “security” coverage that a given security force can effectively provide could possibly expand with the introduction of various technologies. Three different types of security are critical in a post-conflict environment and have been determined to be necessary requirements for a SPEYES security system for our forces (force protection), security for the locals (population protection), and security

for critical infrastructures (critical infrastructure protection). Some force multiplier technologies that might be exploited to provide the needed security might include tracer RFIDs, swarming UV's, multi-spectral cameras, crowd dynamics modeling, dynamic planning, smart scheduling, non-lethals, along with other possibilities.

3. SPEYES Experiment: Basic Constructs

To address these goals, we developed a flexible, controllable, distributed simulation/experimental paradigm suitable for examining the security dynamics in a post-conflict mission environment and for quantifying the potential performance improvements of a SPEYES system over current practices. This simulation model captures many of the key SASO system dynamics that the SPEYES system will need to address.

The purpose of our simulation model was to show the improvements in both *efficiency* and *effectiveness* achieved with the SPEYES system. Operational efficiency focuses on maintaining the same degree of force protection, while decreasing the number of personnel, amount of equipment, and cost and/or resources needed to sustain a particular level of protection. Effectiveness is defined by improved force protection and incident prevention. This includes protecting, reducing harm and damage to US and host nation personnel in terms of numbers Killed-in-action (KIA) and Wounded-in-action (WIA), thwarting planned attacks by insurgents, decreasing the amount of damage and number of attacks sustained by US equipment and the host nation's infrastructure.

3.1. Military Context for Simulation Scenario

To create our simulated scenario, we utilized a military scenario similar to that used at the National Training Center in Ft. Irwin, California, where Tiefert City, a simulated third world city in the Mojave Desert, is used for urban warfare training. US and coalition forces are conducting multi-phase operations to maintain security and stability in the simulated Tiefert City (TC), which is an area of 5x5 square miles containing 38 buildings with a population of 200 Iraqis. US Forces are composed of 1 Battalion and 4 Companies.

ALPHA and DELTA companies are dedicated to reconnaissance operations; CHARLIE and BRAVO companies are assigned to cordon, search, and secure operations in TC. The latter two companies are decomposed into 6 Platoons, comprised of 26 Squads. Special Operations Forces (SOF) embedded in the city for the last 3 months, report that insurgency in the city is growing. Recent intelligence suggests that local government is on the verge of collapse and the security of a power plant – the only source of electricity in the area – is threatened. Surrounding area reconnaissance including the hills around TC and the route from Forward Operating Base (FOB) to TC, has been conducted by the ALPHA and DELTA companies. Currently, CHARLIE and BRAVO companies have moved from their position at FOB to the entrance of TC and are ready to commence operations to secure the power plant in Tiefert City and suppress the

insurgency. The insurgents are threatening friendly forces with Improvised Explosive Devices (IEDs), Rocket-Propelled Grenade (RPG) attacks, Vehicle-Borne Explosives (VBIEDs), and Sniper attacks. Several enemy fighter groups have been seen in the city. It is suspected that insurgents have several bases with weapons caches, which must be found and secured to eliminate further attacks. The situation is exacerbated by the fact that the city population's trust in local officials is low. Local paramilitary forces have remained neutral, but intelligence indicates their high sensitivity to any violence and/or civilian casualties.

The area of responsibility and geography map of the scenario is shown in Figure 5. The objectives of CHARLIE and BRAVO companies are to stop the violence, establish control over the city, secure critical infrastructure, and achieve a return to normalcy in which routine civil and economic activities can take place without disruption. To accomplish these goals, friendly forces must conduct building searches to find and secure weapons caches, interrogate suspected insurgents, search and neutralize snipers and foreign fighters, conduct surveillance, clear and secure strategic buildings, avoid IEDs, prevent VBIED attacks, secure the power plant, establish check points, and deal with crowds in the city.

Figure 5. Simulation Scenario Area of Responsibility

3.2. Scenario Challenges and Vignettes

Upon entering the city, friendly forces encounter enemy resistance which manifests itself in various attacks by the enemy against US and coalition forces. In our simulated environment, we address key challenges of the urban operations. These challenges are defined as scenario *vignettes* (events) which are discussed below.

Improvised explosive devices (IEDs).

The first key challenge is the protection of friendly forces against improvised explosive devices (IEDs) which are possibly the most potent means of violence in the hands of insurgents and terrorists. IEDs have been used extensively in Iraq for several reasons: they

can be planted at the place of insurgents and terrorists' choosing and detonated at a preselected time via remote control; they are easy and inexpensive to design and build; and they have a tremendous psychological effect on the local population. Innovative technologies to detect and destroy IEDs could result in a reduction in manning considering the many tasks associated with protection of roads, markets, residences, etc., and also the possibility of casualties since human explosives ordinance disposal (EOD) teams are needed to disarm IEDs.

For purposes of our simulation, we modeled two types of IEDs: (a) remotely detonated; and (b) hard-wired. In our simulation, IEDs detonate when friendly forces come within the kill range of the IED. Jamming protection of the forces from RF-detonated IEDs is modeled by decreasing the IED's kill range, where hard-wired IEDs are modeled as non-detectable.

Enemy Snipers.

Another key challenge is detecting and neutralizing snipers. Besides causing civilian and military casualties, snipers can hamper day-to-day civil activities and hurt morale. Using incendiary or armor-piercing bullets, snipers armed with high-powered rifles can also threaten lightly armored vehicles and hovering or landing helicopters.

In our simulation, we modeled a sniper as a single enemy combatant who selectively engages targets from a location that offers superior fields of view. We model two types of snipers: (a) regular snipers; and (b) embedded snipers. Regular snipers are located at rooftops or windows, and are easily detectable if they fire on the friendly forces. Embedded snipers on the other hand are located deep within the buildings and are not easily detectable. When detected, regular snipers can be neutralized by helicopter or tank fire, or engaged by mobile fire teams. Embedded snipers must be engaged by anti-sniper teams, because heavy fire near their location might result in civilian casualties.

Rocket-Propelled Grenades (RPGs).

A shoulder-fired rocket propelled grenade (RPG) is a very potent weapon. Designed specifically for close combat operations, this simple and affordable weapon poses a serious threat to even the heaviest tanks, against convoys, isolated checkpoints, observation posts, and in certain conditions against low, slow-flying or hovering helicopters.

For the purposes of our simulation, we consider only RPG attacks against convoys and light-skinned vehicles. Due to weapons specifics, the RPG carriers are very elusive (firing an RPG from 200-400 meters, and leaving the scene immediately), and are hard to detect before the engagement with current capabilities.

Persistent Surveillance.

To provide security in the city, surveillance checkpoints must be established. This means that significant amounts of manpower are needed. In addition to more general surveillance requirements, SASO missions in urban environments may require continuous monitoring of a building or fairly small area. There may be a need to observe or listen to activities in a particular room; to monitor personnel, equipment, or vehicles entering or leaving a building; or to otherwise observe activities at a town square, park, or other fixed site. Some existing ISR platforms using EO, IR, or radar sensors have sufficient resolution to accomplish these missions covertly from medium to high altitudes. However, if the mission requires identifying either a particular person, a small piece of equipment, or a small package entering or leaving a building, then ISR platforms operating at standoff distances may not be sufficient. In addition, a police-like stakeout by a ground squad in a nearby or adjacent area may be necessary. In our scenario, we model several events that require monitoring of the buildings and streets throughout the city.

Mobile Surveillance.

If the mission requires finding the origin or perpetrators of the attacks, following and/or identifying the suspects might be required. Currently, major challenges exist in detecting, identifying, and tracking human targets using ISR platforms operating at standoff distances, especially in urban areas with the presence of obstructions such as buildings, canopies, foliage, camouflage, etc. exist. An alternative ground-based approach is to put friendly ground forces throughout the city, manning observation posts and roadblocks, patrolling, and generally making it difficult for adversary forces to move without detection. In our simulation, we assumed enemy attackers return to their points of origin; hence, detecting, identifying, and tracking using a ground-based approach would allow finding and securing these sites to prevent future attacks.

Securing buildings and weapons caches.

When weapons – conventional, chemical, or biological, – and/or explosives caches are discovered, they should be secured from access by both enemy and non-

combatants. Due to the possibility of casualties, detonating conventional explosives in populated urban areas is risky. To keep the weapons out of the hands of terrorists, significant manpower is needed to secure and guard these sites. In our simulations, we designed several militia bases and weapons cache sites, with the goal of neutralizing (finding and securing) them in order to prevent future attacks on friendly forces.

Vehicle-borne IEDs (VBIEDs).

SASO operations often require friendly forces to control city streets. The amount of control may vary by situation: militias, irregulars, and various combatant forces must be denied the freedom to mass, move, and operate, whether on foot, in modified civilian vehicles, or in armored vehicles. One of the more challenging problems is neutralizing VBIEDs. Currently, not only is identification of the explosives difficult even at established checkpoints, but also preventing the movement of the vehicles when in close proximity to the checkpoint or convoy without inflicting civilian casualties is a challenge. In our simulation, we modeled explosives carried on vehicles to detonate on impact or at a predefined location/time.

Infrastructure search.

To establish security in the city, search operations must be conducted. Both ground sensor networks and airborne platforms have the potential to reduce the manpower demands and risks to friendly forces associated with these operations. Although friendly ground forces are likely still to be required, they could be more effective if cued to problem areas by unmanned sensors. In our simulation, we establish search points that require friendly ground forces to conduct search and secure operations throughout the city.

Crowd control.

At various stages of urban operations and SASO, military forces are confronted with crowds consisting of non-combatants, in addition to armed and violent militia. Crowd characteristics and behaviors are important factors when considering the appropriate actions. In our simulation, we have created vignettes of crowds of various sizes and hostility levels that friendly forces would have to deal with.

3.3. US and Coalition Forces

The US and coalition command organization and force composition that conduct the SASO operations is shown in Figure 6. The forces consists of assets from two companies (CHARLIE and BRAVO), as well as battalion-level force assets. Each company is comprised of three platoons controlled by individual commanders. Each platoon is comprised of two operations (OPS) units (a joint configuration of a Tank and a Bradley), an engineering squad (ENGR), four mobile fire teams (MFTs), and two anti-sniper teams (AST). The OPS unit carries two MFT and AST teams on a Bradley vehicle, and dispatches them to conduct operations inside the city. Company CHARLIE and BRAVO commanders are responsible for coordinating their assigned platoons. At the battalion level, there is an explosive ordinance disposal (EOD) squad, three military police (MP) squads dealing with detainees and conducting interrogations, two helicopters (HELO) conducting fire support, three medical squads (MED), two unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), two allied police (POL) squads, and a Q-36 radar.

In this effort, we modeled various existing and emerging technologies that address the challenges outlined in last section; we also assumed the technologies were integrated into a single SPEYES

system. The performance profiles for each of the technologies simulated is too detailed to provide in this paper. To assess the performance effects of the various SPEYES technologies in terms of force multiplier payoffs, we simulated and then compared three organizational configurations for the forces: (i) the organization outlined in Figure 6 without SPEYES technologies, (ii) the organization outlined in Figure 6 with SPEYES technologies, and (iii) half the organization outlined in Figure 6 with SPEYES technologies.

3.4. Modeling Paradigm

Our simulation utilizes modeling of four major entities: *Assets, Tasks, Resources, and Commanders*.

Assets are controllable and/or movable units, e.g.:

- Individual weapons, or weapon systems
- Sensors, UAVs, radars
- Human teams of any granularity level (squad, platoon, company, etc.)

Assets are used to *process* (execute) tasks which involve activities such as attack, kill, observe, apply, negotiate, etc. Attributes defining the assets include: velocity, maneuver constraints, resource capability,

Figure 6. US and Coalition Forces Organization: (SPEYES technologies in bold red and italic blue)

attack range, identification range, kill range, etc.

Tasks are activities/events that require certain resources for successful execution with appropriate friendly assets. Tasks are generated from a mission plan or event list, and can represent:

- Individual targets or enemy actions;
- Location of the search to be conducted;
- Rescue operations, defense and attack;
- Monitor; etc.

The following attributes must be specified in order to define a task: location/movement, appearance time, dynamics, resource requirements, precedence constraints, etc.

Resources are quantitative representations of what assets can do during the mission (*asset resource capabilities*) and what tasks are required for successful processing (*task resource requirements*). This means that resources identify the following parameters of the distinct individual capabilities and/or requirements:

- Volume/strength (e.g., OPS has strong Fire capability due to its on-board guns; power plant requires two fire teams to be secured);
- Range (UAV can identify vehicles at a range of five miles);
- Context (MP cannot neutralize an embedded sniper); etc.

The manner in which we *model* the capabilities of the various assets and weapons has proven itself to be extremely flexible in past efforts (Kleinman *et al.*, 1996), (Levchuk *et al.*, 2002a,b), (Kleinman *et al.*, 2003). The paradigm adopted for our model-driven experiments first defines a set/vector of resources $R = [r_1, r_2, \dots]$ that is relevant to the problem context at hand. Each element r_i defines a resource category or warfare area. Then, every *asset* is assigned a numerical value for each element r_i , which defines that asset's *resource capabilities vector*. In addition, each *task* that is contained within the scenario is assigned a *vector of resource requirements*. The paradigm requires the team to prosecute tasks in such a way that a task's resource requirements are met by the summed resource capabilities of the assets allocated to that task. Thus, resource requirements and capability modeling is used to find asset-to-task allocation.

Commanders are human decision-makers who have the ownership/control over their assigned resources

/assets, make decisions about what tasks to select for execution and with what assets, and need to communicate to synchronize assets and decide on task selection and asset employment. The *command structure* which specifies authority and supported-supporting relationships among the commanders is determined by the battalion commander.

3.5. Resource Categories and Asset Capabilities

For our simulations, we selected the following set of resource categories:

$R = [\text{FIRE, AST, MED, EOD, MP, SECR, CLR, ISR, IPOL, CALM, ACOU, DEW, SRCH, VSTOP}]$

where:

- FIRE = ability to shoot at targets
- AST = counter-sniper capability/requirement
- MED = medical attention capability/requirement
- EOD = counter-explosive
- MP = policing
- SECR = securing buildings
- CLR = clearing mines and road blocks
- ISR = surveillance and intelligence gathering
- IPOL = Iraqi policing squad with non-lethal weapons for crowd control
- ACOU = directed acoustic energy
- DEW = directed energy wave
- SRCH = search of buildings
- VSTOP = stop vehicles by HPM

With these definitions, the capabilities of the assets for the US and coalition forces are given in Table I.

3.6. Scenario Tasks

In our simulations, we define a *task* as an activity that requires execution by friendly forces and is either predefined from a mission plan or must be performed to respond to mission events (e.g., enemy activities). From the vignettes described in subsection 3.2, we developed scenario tasks. Tasks are distinguished by resources required for successful execution and the following three attributes:

- (i) *hostility* – identifies the level of hostility of the task towards the friendly force;

- (ii) *size* – identifies the presence signature or size of the enemy force;
- (iii) *duration* – identifies the time it takes the friendly force to process the task; and
- (iv) *armed* – identifies the strength of attack against the friendly forces.

Resource Capabilities														
Name	Description	FIRE	AST	MED	EOD	MP	SECR	CLR	ISR	IPOL	ACOU	DEW	SRCH	VSTOP
Platforms														
OPS	Tank/Bradley squad	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
MED	Ambulance	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ENG	Engineers Squad	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
MP	Military Police Squad	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
UAV	Unmanned Air Vehicle	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
HELO	Helicopter	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Explosive Ordnance														
EOD	Disposal Squad	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Q36	Radar	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IPOL	Allied Police Squad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
UAUVS	SPEYES UAV	0	1	0	0	1	1	0						
Sub-Platforms														
MFT	Mobile Fire Team	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
AST	Anti-sniper team	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
REOD	Robotic EOD	0	0	0	1	0								
Weapons and Technologies														
FOAM	Non-lethal Foam	0	0	0	0	0	1	0						
CAM	MSI Camera Cluster	0	1	0	0	0	0	0						
SNIF	Explosive Sensor Grid	0												

Table I. US/Coalition Assets and Resource Capabilities (SPEYES technologies in bold red)

The task attributes for our simulated scenario are shown in Table II. In the Tiefert City scenario, the activity of enemy (RED) forces included 13 attacks with IEDs, 5 attacks using VBIEDs, 4 coordinated RPGs attacks, 21 snipers (7 inside buildings, 14 on rooftops), 3 detainees requiring military police interrogation, 5 crowd control situations of varying hostility and sizes; 6 weapons caches, 7 medical first aid incidents, and 11 potential casualty evacuations.

To execute the tasks, decision makers (commanders) follow a multi-stage process (Figure 7). When the task appears in the scenario, it should first be detected with appropriate sensors. Second, the task must be measured to identify the task’s attributes. When the task is selected for execution, the assets that will prosecute this task must be allocated. This is done according to task resource requirements, asset resource capabilities, task and asset attributes, current utilization of assets (location, assignment), and “attack” and “be attacked” ranges of the assets. Then, the selected assets are moved by decision makers using appropriate commands/controls into position within the “attack” range for the task. When assets come into position to execute the task, they start the attack phase, which takes the time specified in the “duration” attribute of the task.

Symbol	Description	Resource Requirements													Attributes					
		FIRE	AST	MED	EOD	MP	SECR	CLR	ISR	IPOL	ACOU	DEW	SRCH	VSTOP	DURATION (min)	SIZE	HOSTILITY	ARMED		
IED	IED - hardwired	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	1	1
IED	IED - RF	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	1	1
STOP	Roadblock	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.67	1	0	0
SN1	Rooftop/window sniper	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.67	1	1	1
SN2	Imbedded sniper	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	1	1
VEH	Vehicle with explosives	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.67	2	1	1
VEH	Vehicle w/o explosives	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.67	2	0	0
VBIED	Vehicle-borne IED	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1.67	2	1	1
PER	RPG firer	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.67	1	1	2
PER	Unarmed hostile	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.67	1	1	0
PER	Armed friendly	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.67	1	0	1
PER	Armed hostile	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.67	1	1	1
PER	Armed hostile group	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.67	2	1	2
EVA	Casualty evacuation	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0
MED	First-aid task	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0
TNT	weapons cache	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1200	3	0	3
BLDG	Building to be secured	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1200	2	1	1
SRCH	Search task	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	20	2	1	1
IEDP	IED - planter	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.67	1	1	1
PWR	Power Plant task	5	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	3	9	1
EYE	Surveillance task	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	200	1	0	0
DET	Detainee task	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	1
TCP	Traffic control point	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	40	1	0	0
SCHP	Security Checkpoint	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.67	3	0	1
CRWD1	Crowd control task-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	5	1	1	1
CRWD2	Crowd control task-2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	2
CRWD3	Crowd control task-3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	5	2	2	0
CRWD4	Crowd control task-4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	5	2	2	1
CRWD5	Crowd control task-5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0

Table II. Tasks Attributes and Resource Requirements

Figure 7. Task Execution Phases

4. DDD Simulation Platform Overview

The Dynamic Distributed Decision-making (DDD) tool (Kleinman *et al.*, 1996) was the simulation tool used in the SPEYES seedling effort. It is a distributed real-time simulation environment implementing a complex synthetic team task that includes many of the behaviors at the core of almost any team task: assessing the situation, planning response actions, gathering information, sharing and transferring

Figure 8. DDD Core Architecture

information, allocating resources to accomplish tasks, coordinating actions, and sharing or transferring resources. Successive DDD generations have demonstrated the paradigm’s flexibility in reflecting different domains and scenarios to study realistic and complex team decision-making. The DDD is used by many researchers, trainers and practitioners worldwide. It has already proven to be an effective testbed for conducting experiments in a number of different tactical environments including the Air Force AWACS, JTF, Naval Battle Group, Army Ground Maneuvers, Army Urban Warfare/Special Ops, NASA Search and Rescue, and Joint Peacekeeping Operations. Figure 9 outlines the core architecture of the DDD simulator, and Figure 10 displays a screenshot of the DDD simulation for a complex Air Operations mission.

5. Force Multiplier Measures

The potential force multiplier payoff measures for the SPEYES technologies are numerous. For the purposes of this effort, we assessed the technologies and the integrated SPEYES system in terms of *timeliness* measures (e.g., throughput, latency, response time), *efficiency* measures (e.g., troops efficiency, assets damaged, casualties), and *effectiveness* measures (secured area as a function of patrol units and incident rates with and without the SPEYES technologies, task completion rate, failed tasks, detection coverage). The following summarizes a representative set of these measures.

One of the measures of timeliness considered in our simulations was the *mission completion time*, which indicates the speed with which the whole mission is completed. The overall *throughput*, which indicates the rate of activities that a friendly organization can

Figure 9. DDD User Interface

perform, is the ratio of the number of tasks processed to the total completion time of these tasks:

$$\text{Overall Throughput} = \frac{\# \text{ of tasks processed}}{\text{completion time}}$$

In our simulations, we have considered throughput measures for different classes of tasks for both task processing and identification (e.g., sensor detection throughput, which identified the rate of detecting IEDs, RPGs, and snipers). One of the important indicators of how efficiently the friendly forces can prevent and suppress enemy activities was a measure of *number of enemy attacks*, which included attacks by IEDs, RPGs, snipers, and enemy fighters. The impact of enemy attacks was assessed in terms of an *overall casualties* measure, which calculated the casualties based on the probability of kill of a specific enemy attack. In the simulations, we assumed the probability of casualty from an IED attack is 50%, and the casualty from a sniper or RPG attack is 20%.

The *troop efficiency* signifies the average number of troops that are available to execute a single troop task:

$$\text{Troop Efficiency} = \frac{\# \text{ of available troops}}{\# \text{ of troop tasks}}$$

where the number of troop tasks (operations) is computed as the tasks that are assigned to human teams and cannot be prevented or executed by other assets. Troop efficiency was also manifested in assessing the load of specific teams. This was done using the metric of *number of engagements* of individual teams (e.g., number of engagements of MFT teams had a significant impact on speed of operations).

Figure 10. Human-in-the-loop Simulation Results: Normalized Performance and Process Measures (Δ = improvement obtained with SPEYES system compared to without SPEYES case)

The measures defined above can be computed for all tasks or for specific task/event classes.

6. Simulation Results

6.1. Human-driven Simulation Results

To assess the impact of the SPEYES system, we conducted a DDD human-in-the-loop experiment. Human participants played the roles of US forces commanders (see Figure 6). Three Tiefert City mission scenarios (without SPEYES system, with SPEYES, and with SPEYES under a 50% troop reduction) have been played by human teams. These runs address the improvements in both efficiency and effectiveness that can be achieved with the SPEYES system. In this section, we present the mean results from those runs, and discuss their implications.

From simulations results (Figure 10) for US and coalition forces with and without SPEYES, we can see that SPEYES provides a significant (46%) reduction in mission completion time (time that it takes to execute Tiefert City mission), a 92% reduction in successful enemy sniper and RPG attacks and 90% reduction in casualties, and significant (48%) improvement in task throughput (number of tasks executed by the organization per hour) and troop utilization efficiency (number of troops available to execute troop tasks). Even in the 50%-reduced force with a SPEYES system, the simulation also shows a significant improvement in performance over regular operations with a full force but without SPEYES, thus confirming the force multiplier effect achievable by utilizing the SPEYES system.

The largest contribution to performance improvements stemmed from the ability of the SPEYES system to *detect the threats earlier* (sensing component), give this information to the soldiers on the ground (SA/C2 component), and be able to neutralize the threats with novel technologies (shaping component). The effect was threefold. First, the soldiers obtained a better situational awareness about the threats that should be avoided while on patrol and conducting regular security operations. Second, the information supplied the troops with the foreknowledge of “hot spots”. This meant that troops had better intelligence about where the tasks (problem areas) were, they obtained this knowledge faster, and were able to act on it (execute tasks) more quickly without redundant searches that would be necessary without the SPEYES system. Additional novel technologies integrated into the SPEYES system have augmented the capability of the US/Coalition organization to prosecute various threats, increasing the speed and decreasing the casualties during the operation. And finally, being able to prosecute enemy activities faster had a preventive effect and led to a reduction in the total number of hostilities throughout the mission.

An example of the above cause-effect can be seen, for example, in the capability of the organization with SPEYES case to detect and neutralize IEDs faster. First, the faster detection provides a better situational awareness to the troops. Second, the robotic EOD technologies allow executing EOD neutralization missions faster and without casualties. As a result, human teams can prosecute their intended missions

faster or the troop size can be reduced to maintain the same mission performance, thus demonstrating the capabilities of SPEYES as a force multiplier.

6.2. Agent-driven Simulation

Agent-based scheduling for the SPEYES system adapted the optimization-based dynamic planning and scheduling agents for the DDD simulator to include features relevant to a SPEYES security system. These included patrol routes, non-uniform spatial-temporal incident processes, and dynamic assignment of SPEYES assets (e.g., multi-spectral cameras, unmanned vehicles, non-lethal weapons, tracer RFIDs, etc). The potential performance improvements of a SPEYES security system in providing mission monitoring, (re)planning and smart scheduling capabilities are assessed in terms of timeliness, efficiency, and effectiveness measures.

Figure 11. DDD-Agent Architecture (SDS - shared data storage; ADS - agent data storage)

6.2.1. Agent Framework

The architecture of the agent-driven simulator is shown in Figure 11. The Shared Data Storage (SDS) provides the DDD state variables (estimates of own and adversary states) that serve as the agent’s situational awareness. The Agent Data Storage (ADS) holds the agent’s normative behaviors that are specific to a given environment (e.g., geographical responsibility for each decision-maker, possible patrol

routes), the various mission monitoring, and (re)planning data and measures.

An intelligent synthetic decision-maker (DM) is a computational agent that is situated in the environment and is capable of flexible autonomous actions in this environment in order to meet its design objectives. In the SPEYES security system, the agents represent a set of cooperative DMs, who share a common objective of successfully completing a set of assigned tasks under resource and time constraints and work together to achieve this common goal. The current implementation of the agent system centralized asset-task assignment, and decentralized task execution, taking into account communication and coordination delays across the team hierarchy (see Figure 12).

In the DDD environment, each DM is equipped with a set of assets that determine the DM’s resource capability and are assigned a set of tasks (individually or as a subteam) with a specific set of resource requirements. Situational awareness in the DDD environment includes the detection (existence), measurement (characteristics), and identification (classification) of tasks, and the monitoring of the DM’s own assets and those of others. The DM’s situational awareness is constrained by the capability of DM’s assets, i.e., the detection, measurement, and identification ranges and accuracies. For example, the DM may not be aware of the existence of a task, if it is outside the DM’s coverage. Such knowledge has to be communicated among DMs within a team (among coordinating partners). The current implementation addresses this issue as a communication delay among DMs, which translates into delays in task execution.

Figure 13. Task Assignment and Processing Procedures

The procedures for the *centralized* task-asset assignment are outlined in Figure 13. Periodically, a set of currently *ready* tasks are assigned to a set of assets for processing. Tasks are allocated to groups of assets such that the aggregated resource capabilities meet or exceed the demands of the task. Task processing in the DDD involves the launching of assets from their parent assets, the traveling of assets from their current locations to the task location, and the pursuing and executing of the task. The execution of a task can only begin when all of its predecessors are completed, and all assets from the assigned asset group arrive at the appropriate locations. Tasks must be executed within a limited time window of opportunity. In addition, an asset can only process one task at a time. The objective task-asset assignment is to distribute the available assets among tasks, such that the overall mission completion time is minimized. A detailed mathematical formulation of the centralized scheduling problem can be found in (Levchuk *et al.*, 2002a&b). Further details of the agent framework can be found in (Meirina *et al.*, 2003).

6.2.2. Agent-driven Simulation Results

First, we conducted simulations to calibrate agent performance to that achieved in human-in-the-loop simulations. The task selection and asset employment strategies performed by agents and humans are hard to calibrate, since humans use preplanning and partial domain knowledge not available to synthetic agents. Hence, there were some differences between the performance of agent simulations and human-in-the-loop runs (Figure 14a). On the other hand, we found that the trends exhibited by human and agent simulations were comparable (see Figure 14b) and indicated the consistent benefits accrued by a SPEYES system.

Next, we conducted sensitivity analysis to evaluate the impact of specific classes of SPEYES technologies. In particular, we wanted to analyze the impact of sensing technologies; SA/C2 technologies; and shaping technologies. The DDD simulations did not explicitly model SA/C2 functionality (e.g., information fusion, integrated threat maps, entity and behavioral threat models, etc.); the agent-based simulations had optimal resource allocation and scheduling algorithms embedded in them. Instead, the performance contributions of the SA/C2 technologies were assumed to be embedded within the sensing and shaping technologies. To show the benefits of SA/C2 functionality, we assumed two-thirds of sensing and shaping performance improvements were attributed to SA/C2 technologies. This resulted in the relative performance improvements of SPEYES component technologies as shown in Figure 14c, with sensing technologies increasing throughput by 11% and decreasing casualties by 29%, SA/C2 technologies increasing throughput by 49% and decreasing casualties by 62%, and shaping technologies increasing throughput by 12% and decreasing casualties by 2%. These results are intuitive and underscore the importance of the system integration component of SPEYES, viz., combined sensing, SA/C2, and shaping technologies.

7. Analytical Modeling Approaches

7.1. Overview

The focus of combined analytical and simulation-based modeling was to investigate the impact of integrating a collection of existing and emerging technologies within a SPEYES security system, viz., the force multiplier needed to establish the desired SASO efficiency payoff given limited numbers of troops. Analytical modeling based on queuing theory, operations research, and crime mapping techniques guided the agent-based simulation-based effort in assessing the impact of security technologies on the stability regions and/or troops.

For example, the Square Root Law (Kolesar and Blum, 1973) states that the response-time T_r of N_0 patrol units is proportional to the square root of the effective area A :

$$E[T_r] \approx \frac{E[D]}{v_c} = \frac{c}{v_c} \sqrt{\frac{A}{N_0(1-\rho)}} \quad (1)$$

where D denotes the traveled distance, v_c signifies the patrol speed, ρ represents the busy (utilization)

Metrics	Human		Agent	
	W/O SPEYES	With SPEYES	W/O SPEYES	With SPEYES
Mission completion time (hours:min)	11:57	6:24	11:48	8:33
# MFT Engagements	73	29	47	20
Total Throughput (tasks per hour)	9.4	18.3	8.1	14.0
# Enemy Attacks (snipers, RPGs, IEDs)	24	2	13	2
Troop efficiency (# troops per troop task)	1.07	2.08	1.07	2
# Casualties	41.5	4	21.9	1.6
Sniper Detection Rate (# of snipers detected/hr)	3.6	10.9	4.5	13.7

(a) One-to-one Comparison of Human and Agent Simulations

(b) Comparison of Improvement Obtained with SPEYES

(Δ= difference between assessments of SPEYES improvement as provided by *Human-in-the-loop* and *Synthetic Agent* simulations)

(c) SPEYES Component Technology Benefits

(Δ = relative improvement compared to W/O SPEYES case)

Figure 14. Agent-Human Calibration Results

rate of the patrol unit and c is a constant. Thus, the effective area of coverage is proportional to the number of idle patrol units and the square of the response time.

$$A = \left[\frac{E[T_r]v_c}{c} \right]^2 N_0(1-\rho) \quad (2)$$

What this law states is the following. Suppose we are able to reduce the response time with SPEYES

technologies from T_{r1} to T_{r2} ($T_{r1} > T_{r2}$) for a given area, A . Then, if we are willing to tolerate the same response time of T_{r1} with and without SPEYES technologies, then a patrol unit with SPEYES

technologies can cover a larger area, $A_2 = A \left(\frac{T_{r1}}{T_{r2}} \right)^2$ or

equivalently, we can reduce the size of the patrol unit to cover the same area.

The key objectives of the modeling effort were the following: (i) the systematic evaluation of the impact of SPEYES technologies; (ii) maximizing the *effective* number of patrols, i.e., troops; (iii) minimizing *response time* to increase the area of coverage (for the same response time).

7.2. Preventive Patrol Model

Preventive patrol constitutes touring an area, with the patrol units scanning for threats and attempting to prevent incidents and intercept any threats in progress. Since preventive patrol is a major aspect of stability operations, the optimal allocation of patrol effort is a key problem to be solved. The spatial-temporal model proposed in this paper enables us to identify “hot spots” by estimating the incident rates in different cells of a patrolled area based on historical data and real-time sensor observations. This information can be used to optimize the frequency of patrol from various cells, and estimate the probability that patrolling units will intercept threats within a patrolled area.

7.2.1. Incident Rate Estimation

We assume that an observation area is divided into N_C “spatial segments (cells)”. The incident rate in each cell j is modeled as a Poisson process with unknown rate equal to $\lambda_j, j=1, \dots, N_C$ incidents per unit time and per unit area. The rate parameter λ_j is assumed to be a Gamma random variable. Assume that there are N patrol units, each of which can travel to any of the geographical cells in the region. The Patrol route is random and is affected by the incidence rates. Finally, only a limited area of coverage (miles) is available for patrol units. Thus, the probability of n ($n \geq 1$) events happening in cell j in an interval $(t, t+\Delta)$ is:

$$p_j(n) = P\{X_j(t) = n | \lambda_j\} = \frac{[\lambda_j \Delta A_j]^n e^{-\lambda_j \Delta A_j}}{n!} \quad (3)$$

where, $X_j(t)$ is the number of incidents and A_j is the area of cell j . The density function of λ_j is given by

$$f(\lambda) = r \lambda^{b_j-1} e^{-c_j \lambda} U(\lambda) \quad (4)$$

where r is the normalization constant and $\{b_j, c_j\}$ are the parameters defining cell j . Using Bayes’ theorem, we obtain

$$f(\lambda_j \Delta | X_j(t) = n) = \frac{(\lambda_j \Delta A_j)^n r (\lambda_j \Delta)^{b_j-1} e^{-c_j \lambda_j \Delta}}{n! P(X_j(t) = n)} \quad (5)$$

which is a *Gamma* distribution, $\Gamma[n_j + b_j, A_j + c_j]$. Thus, λ_j can be updated using the following formula:

$$\lambda_j^{new} \Delta = \frac{b_j + n_j}{c_j + A_j} \quad (6)$$

where n_j is the number of incidents observed by sensors in cell j . This formula can also be written as a recursive estimation of new λ_j :

$$\lambda_j \Delta \leftarrow \lambda_j \Delta + \frac{A_j}{c_j + A_j} \left(\frac{n_j}{A_j} - \lambda_j \Delta \right) \quad (7)$$

7.2.2. Estimation of Intercept Probability

We define l_j equal to the intercept distance in cell j (travel distance in cell j) and e_j equal to the number of patrols that traveled through the cell j during patrol sweep. Accordingly, the average effective travel distance L per cell is equal to

$$L = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_C} e_j l_j}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_C} e_j} \quad (8)$$

It is assumed that the passing of cell j from a particular direction forms a renewal process. Thus, the mean time between patrol entries into the cell is given by:

$$t_j = \frac{L}{v_c e_j} \quad (9)$$

where v_c denotes the patrol speed. The average *patrol frequency* of cell j (number of patrols entering the cell per unit of time) is defined as:

$$v_j = \frac{v_c e_j}{L} \quad (10)$$

Since we assume that the patrol is random and the incidents in each cell are independent of those in other cells, it can be shown that, in the steady state, the probability of coverage of cell j by a patrol moving with a speed of v_c and length of patrol T in sweeping distance L is given by:

$$PC_j = 1 - e^{-v_c T e_j / L} = 1 - e^{-v_j T} \quad (11)$$

where T denotes the available patrol time. Thus, the joint probability that at least one incident occurs and at least one incident is covered by a patrol in cell j during an interval of duration T is given by:

$$PI_j = pr\{X_j(T) \geq 1 | \lambda_j\} [1 - e^{-v_j T}] \quad (12)$$

where $pr\{X_j(T) \geq 1 | \lambda_j\}$ denotes the probability of at least one incident taking place in cell j .

The objective here is to maximize the average intercept probability PI with respect to patrol passage frequency v_j of cells $j = 1, \dots, N_C$:

$$\max PI = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_C} pr\{X_j(T) \geq 1 | \lambda_j\} [1 - e^{-v_j T}]}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_C} pr\{X_j(T) \geq 1 | \lambda_j\}} \quad (13)$$

subject to a limited aggregate patrol distance coverage, which is defined as:

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N_C} v_j l_j T = \Phi(\text{miles}) \quad (14)$$

where $\Phi(\text{miles})$ is the total distance of patrol routes. The solution to this problem is as follows:

-
- Step 1:** Calculate $pr\{X_j(T) \geq 1 | \lambda_j\}$ for each cell j via eq. (3) where the incident rate λ_j is updated according to eq. (5)
- Step 2:** Sort $\{pr\{X_j(T) \geq 1 | \lambda_j\}, j = 1, \dots, N_C\}$ in descending order
- Step 3:** Assign patrols from the cell with highest $pr\{X_j(T) \geq 1 | \lambda_j\}$ to the cell with lowest $pr\{X_j(T) \geq 1 | \lambda_j\}$
- Step 4:** If constraint as stated in eq. (14) is violated, STOP, otherwise, repeat **Step 3**
-

7.2.3. Analytical Results

Two performance measures were utilized to evaluate the impact of SPEYES technologies: (i) the intercept probability gain (Δ_1); and (ii) the daily casualty reduction (Δ_2) averaged over a month (30 days). The measures are defined in eq. (15) and eq. (26), respectively:

$$\Delta_1 = \frac{1}{30} \sum_{i=1}^{30} \left(\frac{PI_{SPEYES}(i) - PI(i)}{PI(i)} \right) 100\% \quad (15)$$

where $PI_{SPEYES}(i)$ and $PI(i)$ are the intercept probability on day i with and without SPEYES, respectively.

$$\Delta_2 = \frac{1}{30} \sum_{i=1}^{30} \frac{C_{SPEYES}(i) - C(i)}{C(i)} 100\% \quad (16)$$

where $C_{SPEYES}(i)$ and $C(i)$ denote the number of daily casualties with and without SPEYES, respectively. The daily casualties $C(i)$ is defined as:

$$C(i) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_C} \lambda_j A_j t (1 - PI_j) P_{c_j} \quad (17)$$

where P_{c_j} is the probability of casualty in cell j (whose values range from 0.1 to 0.3)

Results, shown in Figure 15, revealed that SPEYES technologies yielded significant improvements: the intercept probability increased by 57%, whereas the daily casualties were reduced by 43%.

Figure 15. Preventive Patrol Simulation Results

7.3. Sensor Evaluation and Smart Scheduling

Real Time SPEYES simulator provided a vehicle to evaluate the impact of SPEYES sensor characteristics (range, accuracy) and barriers, as well as smart scheduling algorithms. The latter were embedded in the DDD agent models.

Figure 16. Real Time Smart Scheduling Simulator Snapshots

Figure 17. Effects (response time, escape rate, casualties) of sensors and barriers

We model the incidents as spatial-temporal random processes, in which insurgents can move randomly. Sensors are parameterized by their coverage, detection probabilities (P_d) and false alarm probabilities (P_f). Patrol units seek to capture insurgents, while avoiding incidents.

Patrol units follow predefined routes without SPEYES (see Figure 16a). The units may be at risk of encountering an incident prior to reaching the

insurgent targets with a certain probability; with SPEYES sensors (Figure 16b and 16c). Patrol units have probabilistic knowledge of the insurgents' locations and the potential incidents. Thus, the patrol units can be rerouted intelligently via smart scheduling to reach the insurgents quickly while minimizing casualties. Without barriers (Figure 16b and 16c), the insurgents are likely to escape from the patrolled area; while with barriers (Figure 16c), the insurgents are more likely to be confined to the region, thereby enhancing the probability of being caught. Smart scheduling, which relies on information from sensors, directs the patrol units to follow the shortest path, while avoiding the incidents. This has the effect of improving the probability of catching insurgents and reducing troop casualties.

Simulation results, shown in Figure 17, demonstrated that a sensor range index (sensor range/casualty range) of 4 or more with good sensor detection ($P_d \geq 70\%$) and frequent sensor data updates, barriers, and smart scheduling can significantly reduce incident response times, decrease insurgent escape rates, and reduce casualties.

8. Conclusions and Future Work

DARPA's SPEYES seedling effort focused on analyzing, simulating, and assessing various integrated C3I technologies that could provide a force-multiplying payoff for three daily-occurring manpower-intensive SASO missions, namely, fixed site security (check points, guard towers), mounted and dismounted patrols, and cordon and search. The focus of this paper was to describe the results of a SPEYES security system that focused on the cordon and search mission. We conducted simulation analysis of the impacts of the proposed system on effectiveness, efficiency, and timeliness of SASO operations on US and coalition forces. Our results show that SPEYES provides a significant reduction in mission completion time, substantial reductions in friendly casualties, large reductions in successful enemy sniper and RPG attacks, and significant improvement in task throughput, and troop utilization efficiencies. Even at 50%-reduced force, a SPEYES system also achieved a significant improvement in performance over regular operations with a full force without SPEYES, thus confirming the force multiplier effect that is achieved by utilizing SPEYES. Our results suggest that significant improvements in manning and operational performance can be achieved by integrating individual novel technologies into a SPEYES system that embraces the improvements in data collection and information dissemination for distributed operations

with advanced shaping technologies, active modeling, and decentralized resource management.

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